

LOW-COST PRODUCTION AND PROCESSING OF LFTS

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ABSTRACT

There is an increasing interest in thermoplastic matrix composites, especially LFTs, mainly due to developments in the automotive industry. However, the high investments required for processing these materials limit their further application in other industries. In the present work a new cost-effective technology of producing powder-coated LFTs and their subsequent processing in an innovative low-cost piston-blender has been studied. It is shown that the production and processing of LFTs using these technologies caused no major problems. Furthermore, the properties of the composites produced are comparable to those of other LFT-materials. Overall, the current work shows the feasibility of these novel LFT-technologies as a low-cost alternative to current LFT-processes.

Keywords: thermoplastic, LFT, towpreg, properties, compression moulding

INTRODUCTION

Recent years have shown an increased interest in the use of thermoplastic matrix composites. This is mainly due to several advantageous properties and speed of processing of these materials as compared to their thermoset counterparts. Among thermoplastic composites, Long Fibre Thermoplastic composites (LFTs) have seen the fastest growth, mainly due to developments in the automotive sector [1].

LFTs combine long (>1 cm) fibres, that provide (semi-)structural material properties, with the ease and speed of thermoplastic processing. A typical installation would comprise of a specially designed extruder where either dry fibres with thermoplastic granules or composite pellets are mixed without fibre breakage. The resulting composite melt is then either injection or compression moulded. The high cost of the equipment involved has limited the use of LFT-technology mainly to the automotive industry, thus not exploiting the many opportunities that lie outside the automotive sector.

The present paper describes the use of a novel low-cost LFT processing technology and the resulting composites. The technology is based on a patented powder-coating machine that produces LFTs directly from fibre roving and matrix material with varying fibre length and content [2,3]. The final quality of impregnation can be tailored to requirement, by selecting only the required processing steps, thus offering the possibility of major production costs savings. The process is able to process virtually any combination of fibre and matrix material and has already shown its usefulness in processes such as fibre impregnated thermoplastic filament winding [4]. The resulting LFTs can be subsequently used in a patented low-cost LFT piston-blender, developed by the Centre of Lightweight Structures (CLS), TUD-TNO, the Netherlands [5,6], that produces a composite melt that can be directly compression moulded into composite plaques. Due to their simplicity, the combination of these LFT technologies results in a process that, at a fraction of the costs of commercially available equipment, can generate LFT-moulded products, with competitive properties, directly from fibre and matrix materials.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

In the present work LFTs were produced using the abovementioned powder-coating technology. ICORENE 9184B P Polypropylene (PP) powder, from ICO Polymers France, with particle size between 60 and 850 μ m, was selected for the matrix material. Owens Corning's 357D-AA, 2400 Tex glass fibres were used as reinforcement. The material properties are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Raw material properties

Property	Units	Glass fibres	Polypropylene
Density	Mg/m ³	2.56	0.91
Tensile strength	MPa	3500	30
Tensile modulus	GPa	76	1.3
Linear roving weight	Tex	2400	-

Powder coating

The powder coating process used to produce the towpregs has been described in detail elsewhere [e.g. 2,3]. In short, the powder-coating line consists of five modules (see Figure 1): i) fibre supplying system; ii) pneumatic spreader; iii) polymer powder feeder and coating chamber; iv) furnace and v) final towpreg wind-up system.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the powder-coating line

The fibres are pulled from the bobbins and are subsequently spread using an pneumatic device to facilitate powder impregnation. Then, the thermoplastic powder, continuously supplied by a feeding extruder, coats the spread fibres in the deposition chamber. The three rolls mounted in the deposition chamber give the possibility of increasing the amount of the powder. The excess of powder is recirculated using an air-fan located at the bottom of the chamber to maintain a polymer cloud. A thermocouple linked to an air-heater allows control of the temperature inside the chamber. To soften the polymer and promote its adhesion to the fibre surface, the material is passed through a furnace. Finally, the thermoplastic matrix towpreg is cooled down and wound-up on the final spool. In this way, glass fibres with adhered, well-distributed, polymer particles can be produced in a continuous process. The current LFTs were obtained in the way described above from towpregs, with a fibre content of 70 wt% (45 vol.%), subsequently cut into 12.5, 25 and 50 mm length sections.

Piston blending and compression moulding

The LFTs were processed in the piston-blender that has been specifically developed to be able to melt LFTs while maintaining fibre length. In this machine, the traditional concept of using an extrusion screw to obtain the required mixing level and melting of LFTs has been abandoned. Instead, a simple

mechanism of rotating heated rods is used to mix and heat the material. Due to the very low shear induced on the melt, fibre breakage is limited to a minimum while accomplishing a sufficient level of mixing. Due to the machine's simple construction, its costs are only a fraction of those of the commercially available LFT-extruders. The machine, therefore, offers the possibility to process LFTs with only minor investments [5].

In Figure 2, a schematic of the machine is shown. The LFTs are fed to the hopper into the piston-blender. The heated rods start rotating and thus mixing the material. At the same time the heat of the cylinder wall (heated by elements from the outside) and the rods, melts the material. When all of the material is molten and properly mixed, moving a piston forward ejects the material that is cut by a cutting device. The material is then ready for compression moulding.

Figure 2. Schematic of CLS' piston-blender

The LFTs described above were fed to the piston-blender and blended together with the virgin PP powder, to obtain composites with varying fibre content. In this way, it was possible to test the effect of fibre length and content on processing and properties. The molten composite materials produced by the piston-blender were compression moulded to 300x300x4 mm³ plates. The processing parameters are given in table 2.

Table 2. Compression moulding processing conditions

Variable	Units	Value
Melt temperature	°C	220
Pressure	MPa	10
Compression time	s	30
Mould temperature	°C	85

Testing

Flexural test specimens (25 x 80 mm) taken from the plates were tested according to ISO 178 at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min, with a total number of 10 samples for each series. To obtain an indication of the level of anisotropy in the moulded plates, flexural test specimens were **cut** in two perpendicular directions. Charpy impact test specimens (15 x 100 mm²) taken from the plates were tested according to ISO 179, with a total number of 10 samples for each series. Fibre content on each tested sample were measured using density tests as well as matrix burn-off tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of fibre volume fraction

The results of the flexural tests (modulus and strength as a function of fibre volume fraction, at a constant fibre length of 25 mm) are given in Figure 3. For comparison, the values obtained in earlier work with a differently LFT-material that was processed in the same way [5], as well as with commercially available GMT, are also given.

Figure 3. Flexural modulus (left) and strength (right) as a function of fibre content

As can be seen from Figure 3, the modulus of the present composites, as expected, increases with increasing fibre content. The increasing spread in results, especially at higher fibre volume fraction, is mainly due to an increasing level of anisotropy, as explained later. It is important to see that the modulus-values are comparable to those obtained with commercially available GMT and previously produced LFTs. This indicates the feasibility of the current processing methodology. On the other hand, the strength data initially increases with increasing fibre content, apparently reaching a limit at higher fibre fractions. This is in agreement with results found on the previously produced LFTs. Here, the influence of the non-optimised fibre-matrix interface of the system studied becomes evident, as the values are lower than those of optimised commercially available GMT. However, it is a known effect that LFT materials show a critical fibre content above which strength decreases with further increase of fibre fraction. The present material (as well as the LFTs previously studied) cross this critical fibre fraction, thus reaching a strength limit, whereas the commercially available GMTs are just not available with fibre contents above X%, which would most likely show similar behaviour.

Effect of fibre length

The results of the flexural tests as a function of fibre length (at a fibre volume fraction of 11%) are given in Figure 4. As can be seen here, although at first instance, and for both properties, a small decrease is seen with increasing length, this effect is negligible considering the spread in results and minor variations in fibre volume fraction between the different samples (13, 10 and 12 % respectively, for the samples with 12.5, 25 and 50 mm fibre length). These quasi-constant values can be explained by the lengths of the fibres studied which are, both for modulus and strength, from a theoretical point of view, above the critical length needed to obtain almost 'continuous fibre' properties [7].

Figure 4. Flexural modulus (left) and strength (right) as a function of fibre length

Level of anisotropy

In Figure 5, the flexural results in perpendicular directions are shown as a function of fibre volume fraction. The indications ‘machine’ and ‘transverse’ do not refer to a distinct process-induced preferred direction, as known with GMTs. They just refer to perpendicular directions chosen for cutting test samples.

Figure 5. Flexural modulus (left) and strength (right) anisotropy as a function of fibre content

The figure shows that in both properties, especially at high fibre loading, the differences between samples taken from the same plate but in perpendicular directions, become very pronounced. This effect is not seen as a function of fibre length. This explains the higher spread in Figure 3 at high fibre fraction, which is an average of the results in both directions. The main reason for these differences is the effect of fibre orientation within the sample, which is supposed to become more pronounced at high volume fractions. It is obvious that, at these levels, it is important to consider anisotropic material properties for the correct design of a final part.

Charpy impact data

In Figure 6 the Charpy impact results are shown as a function of fibre volume fraction. For direct comparison, the values obtained at different fibre lengths are also shown in the figure, as well as the values for GMT and the previously studied LFTs. As can be seen, impact strength seems to increase only slightly with fibre content, although a strong conclusion cannot be drawn considering the spread in values. However, a strong dependency of impact strength on fibre length seems to exist: values increase with increasing fibre length, a known effect in this type of composite materials. The absolute

values, however, are still below those of the other systems, which again is attributed to a non-optimised fibre-matrix adhesion.

Figure 6. Charpy impact strength as a function of fibre volume and fraction length

CONCLUSIONS

The present work showed that the production and processing of a new type of LFT materials can be carried out without major problems. The properties of the composites obtained are at a level comparable to other LFT-materials. Effects of fibre length and volume fraction are in accordance with expectations and previously found results. Improvements in the fibre-matrix interface of the current system should lead to better strength and impact properties. Overall, the system (material and technology) has proven its feasibility as a low-cost alternative to current LFT-processes.

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